

METHODS OF TEACHING ECOLOGY AND ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION

Khushvaktova Kh.S.

Uzbek State World Languages University, Department of Natural Sciences.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14561323>

Abstract. *The given article discusses the theoretical methodology of teaching ecology and science in higher education, the formation of new approaches to the development of environmental education in the context of global warming, and the strategy for the formation of environmental awareness in humanitarian studies in environmental crises. The typology and methodology of teaching ecology and nature conservation is described.*

The methodology of teaching ecology and nature conservation is based on state educational standards adopted by the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Today, almost all universities and professional colleges in the country teach ecology. The number of hours prescribed for a lesson may be more, sometimes less, in some curricula. Using these methods, each student chooses those methods that he considers the most convenient and which he will use in the future when studying natural sciences. The student will further strengthen the unity of knowledge and education, and the professional training of the future teacher will be further expanded.

The environmental doctrine of the country determines the implementation of the environmental policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, primarily through environmental education, upbringing and training.

Keywords: *ecology, teaching methodology, students, higher educational institutions, environmental awareness, environmental education, methodology? interactive, nature.*

It is known that serious attention to the science of ecology began, mainly, in the 21st century, ecology as a science began to be taught in higher educational institutions, certain hours were allocated to ecology in the curriculum. As a result, methods for conducting ecology lessons were quickly formed. According to Ponomareva O.N. (1999), I.T. Suravegina was the first in domestic pedagogy to apply the correlation method and achieved a positive result in mastering ecology. I.T. Suravegina (1989) achieved environmental education of children at school: stories, lectures, conversations, environmental games in lessons.

I.M. Cheredov (1988) joined the method of I.T. Suravegina and initially used the methods of this scientist in the methodology of teaching ecology and offered his additions. Love for the environment through preparation for independent work, book work, observation, creativity, applique, drawing, herbarium, collecting, practical work, competitions, analysis, rewarding, critical attitude, giving examples and general pedagogical work is recommended by the training.

It is highly recommended to increase the love for the environment through the trainings, preparation for independent work, working on books, conducting observations, creativity, applications, drawing, creating herbarium, collecting, conducting practical work, organizing competitions, analysis, rewarding, critical attitude, giving examples and general pedagogical work.

Sharikova G.V. (1997) also suggested to use active methods in the study of ecology, particularly regarding students being involved in scientific activities from the time of their studies at university, conducting field experiments, participating at observation methods, organizing

phenological phases, counting, searching for living organisms, doing statistical measurements, biometric measurements, visiting reserves, plants and animals that involve observations.

D.N. Kavtaradze (1997) believes that environmental education through interactive methods will give results in teaching methodology.

Environmental education means understanding environmental crises and active conservation and protection of nature, the formation of ideas and thoughts about nature conservation in each person.

A pressing environmental problem in the modern system of environmental education is the formation of opportunities for mutual harmony and unity in nature and society. In order to achieve the formation of a society through a continuous and safe system of environmental education, it is necessary to develop the methodology of teaching ecology and nature conservation in universities. To date, very little research has been conducted on the methods of educational systems in the field of ecology and environmental science that meet modern requirements. The study of the conducted scientific research showed that the methodology of teaching ecology in universities has been practically not studied, most of the conducted scientific research was work related to the science of biology and pedagogy.

Malozemova I.I. (2017) wrote in her work that the main task in teaching the methods of environmental education depends on the knowledge, skills of the teacher and the height of the environmental culture formed in his mind. Thanks to the teaching method, the teacher and student learn a certain subject through actions. One of the goals of using various teaching methods is to convey knowledge to the student's consciousness and expand his knowledge.

Nowadays, there are a number of methods of teaching environmental sciences, and the application of these methods can be quite complex and at the same time simple. Because the science of ecology, unlike other sciences, implements methods in natural objects or in their study.

Indeed, according to general didactic requirements, all elements of social experience are mastered in teaching ecology, in particular: the adequacy of the scientific material being studied is taken into account and the student's requests are taken into account, in which it is important to communicate with the student and make the teacher believe in his knowledge, be able to convey information and express himself. The methodology of teaching ecology is not someone's personal methodology, but traditional methods of all subjects are used. The types of teaching methods can be similar or different from other subjects. The famous scientist I. Ya. Lerner (1981) mentioned this in his work.

The following methods are used to study ecology and environmental protection:

1. Oral method – story, lecture, conversation;
2. Demonstration method;
3. Method of working with a book;
4. Interactive method, discussion, analysis of specific environmental situations;
5. Educational games – “on the table”, computer, role-playing, simulation or sign, design, work games;
6. Control method: oral, written, software;
7. Brainstorming.

Lecture. Conducting classes using the lecture method is the most common method in the higher education system. The age of the student sitting in the audience corresponds to the lecture method. We have lessons on ecology and environmental protection at stage 2 for the needs of the

humanitarian direction. Before this, the student listened to lectures on a number of subjects in accordance with the curriculum at stage 1 and is more adapted to listening to lectures and learning. The lecture method involves explaining a certain topic to a student on a scientific basis, conveying important issues of the curriculum, its content, essence, processes and patterns. The absence of lesson hours on ecology always indicates a shortage of lecture hours. The structure of the lesson on the topic covered in the lecture is created on the basis of a clear plan and is recorded by the student. Sometimes students do not have enough textbooks, and even in such cases, recorded lectures allow students to master the subject well. A properly organized and conducted lecture is one of the active teaching methods, in which the teacher thinks at a high level and transfers his knowledge to the student. At a lecture, a teacher can be considered to have conducted a lecture skillfully only if he can convey his thoughts during the lecture, form environmental ideas in the minds of the student and encourage him to follow him.

The speaker is a strong teacher-didactician if he can consolidate and repeat the student's environmental knowledge and leave room for questions. The conversation method is teaching through dialogue, and this is a method that can be used in seminars and during the lesson. Khaidarova H., Bakhadirova Z. and Yakubzhonova Sh. (2009) write that the lack of classroom hours indicates that the conversation method is rarely used in ecology.

Thus, *this teaching method* is less often used in ecology lessons, before showing certain natural phenomena in video shows, this reality is explained. This time, the situation is explained through a conversation. The conversation allows you to express the topic expressively and coherently. Because it is better to first give the student an understanding than to suddenly show natural disasters on video. For example, before showing large typhoons, explaining their causes will allow the student to better absorb this knowledge.

B. Interview method - with this method, the teacher consistently prepares questions on the topic and gives students auxiliary and additional questions. After the teacher asks the students questions, he listens to their answers, and at the same time decides whether the answers are correct or incorrect. Each student independently prepares an answer to the question, uses his knowledge, creatively thinks over each question, makes riddles. The teacher checks the student's answer, corrects it if necessary, and answers all questions during the interview. This method is important as a conclusion or generalization when checking knowledge after studying a certain section.

The debate method is used on specific topics, for example, on the topic of "Global warming and its negative consequences", using this method you can conduct a lesson by involving students. At this time, the teacher tells them the name of the subject that will be in the next lesson and asks them to come prepared. At the beginning of the lesson, the teacher himself gives a certain concept and asks who imagines the consequences of global warming. At this time, the students express their thoughts. As a mature, knowledgeable person, the student shares his opinion with many people and listens to the opinions of others. This method is sometimes called the problem-based learning method. This situation teaches the student to defend his opinion, relying on science, but the student learns that he must also respect the opinions of others during the debate.

Teaching ecology using the demonstration method. When teaching ecology, it is important for the teacher to have a high level of scientific, theoretical and practical knowledge so that he can convey environmental knowledge to the student. When conducting classes using demonstration methods, the question arises of a broader and more meaningful delivery of educational material to the student. Since ecology is a science related to natural phenomena, through the perception of

phenomena and situations in nature and independent coming to certain conclusions, teaching lessons through visual material is highly effective. With this method, lessons are conducted both verbally and practically. The advantage of this method is that both methods are combined, the student first hears and then sees these situations and events, in this process the student has the opportunity to think about what he heard and saw. Instead of simply hearing about what is happening in various environmental objects, for example, the destruction of biodiversity, the reduction of plant and animal species, this animal was there, and now it is completely gone, the student feels differently. In this case, the student himself tries to preserve nature and his inclination to conduct experiments increases.

The demonstration method, in turn, is divided into the methods of illustration, demonstration and observation. The illustrative method includes the presence of pictures, diagrams, charts, posters on the topic with the teacher, as well as the process of using the board. Pictures or tables on a specific topic are prepared and brought by the teacher, and the teacher uses the board to make the lesson more understandable.

Demonstration is a way of demonstrating situations and events related to a specific topic using technical means, films, videos and online broadcasts. In visual lessons, information is conveyed to the student by visualizing and consolidating or compressing information. 1. This can be graphics, images or creative exhibitions, geographical maps that depict various environmental phenomena. Providing information in this case teaches are required to think creatively or think.

The observation method is one of the widely used methods in ecology, which implies that the student learns about changes and events in the external environment through their own observations. In this case, students will receive visual material by observing nature, seeing changes in living organisms with their own eyes, independently studying adaptation, reproduction of populations, and the interdependence of organisms. These ecological methods combine and strengthen the theoretical and practical knowledge of the student.

Practical methods of teaching ecology. Observations by this method give positive results. Ecology and environmental science differ from other humanities in that its study includes observations, experiments, solving various examples and problems, as well as practical experience conducted by students. Based on this method, practical methods can be as follows. Count animals in winter, look at their tracks and determine in advance what kind of animal it is, where it goes. This method is followed by the EcoGairon center, located in Bukhara region. Every year, October 30 is the day of counting animals in the center. In this observation, with the help of many people, all the animals in the EcoCenter and the number of animals roaming freely over a large area were counted. Or the work of determining the number of earthworms per square meter was done by students without difficulty. Together with the students, the teacher divides one square meter into 45-50 cm. They dug deep, collected the worms present in this area, placed them in a bowl of water and counted them. The greater the number of earthworms, the higher the fertility of the soil in this area, and earthworms were considered an ecological indicator of the soil. Conducting such practical experiments gives the student pleasure, launches his scientific research and, as a result, helps to participate in observing nature and consolidates environmental knowledge.

In the practical method, the student gradually consolidates and implements the acquired theoretical knowledge, and the role of the teacher in this situation is very important. In this method, the acquired knowledge and skills of the student are formed and deepened. The student directly conducts the experiment with the help of the teacher, the students are divided into groups and 2-3

of them do the practical work, the rest follow under the guidance of the teacher. The head of the practice, the teacher corrects errors and shortcomings in the work performed. At the end of the experiment, the teacher gives a special description of the work done by each student and the completion of the task.

In fact, as a result of conducting experiments, the student learns to do scientific work, if he has an inclination for scientific work, then in the future he will follow the path of scientific research related to nature. Thus, he learns to do the work correctly, understands the goal, analyzes the tasks, chooses a place for the experiment, effectively uses the necessary tools and equipment. The laboratory method is the method of conducting independent experiments in teaching ecology and nature conservation. It is not possible to study the science of ecology and nature conservation by the laboratory method in all higher educational institutions. When the university specializes in the field of ecology, then laboratories will be equipped in special departments in which it will be possible to conduct laboratory observations on ecology. In the case of a laboratory, students acquire knowledge and skills to master science in the process of conducting experiments. For example, determining the amount of harmful gases in the atmosphere of the city of Tashkent; or determining the amount of dust on tree leaves in Tashkent. There will be laboratory equipment for conducting such analysis as identifying indicator birds in the canals and streams of the city of Tashkent, and the student will conduct the experiment with his own hands under the guidance of a teacher. In this case, the teacher and the student prepare for the experiment together. If a laboratory method is used, the student will develop an interest in scientific research.

When conducting laboratory work, didactic principles are observed, according to which the place and time of the experiment are determined in advance. During the experiments, the student studies a number of methods, studies experiments conducted by other scientists in order to do the work correctly, and in this process, his theoretical and practical knowledge is further consolidated. Laboratory work can be simple or complex, depending on the purpose of the experiment and what they are trying to determine. For example, in the case of determining the purity of water, samples are taken from reservoirs over a large area and the purity of the water is tested in the laboratory using special preparations. If it is necessary to identify radioactive substances in underground water, then the tests are carried out in modern equipped laboratories. Today, many universities do not have laboratories for consolidating environmental knowledge, but today's changes show confidence that in the near future, new laboratory equipment and the ability to use new technologies in the educational system will be provided to universities of the republic. When conducting classes in such a laboratory-practical way, in the minds of students, the educational activities are transferred from a simple lesson to reflection and practice in order to obtain the necessary empirical results.

Methods of working with books in the study of ecology and nature conservation. The method of working with textbooks or specific literature is one of the most basic methods of studying each subject. When a teacher first enters the classroom, regardless of the subject, he first introduces the student to the most necessary literature (in this case, the teacher brings the literature to the classroom and tells the students about its author, when the textbook was published and by which publisher). There are several methods of independent work of students with textbooks or additional literature.

1. The method of taking notes from a textbook is understood as rereading the previous topic to get a brief summary;

2. Writing a thesis - after reading the topic, the student writes down his thoughts;
3. Quoting from the text - when reading, copy some important sentences verbatim (the author, title of the work, publisher, year of publication and page are indicated);
4. Summarize the topic - write a brief description of the material read;
5. Essay writing - research and write other information on a specific topic, when the student finds information that is not in the textbook, covers the topic, acquires new knowledge, works on himself and deepens his knowledge in the field of ecology.
6. Preparation of reference books, etc. - the student collects information on the topic he wants to study and prepares information on the area he considers necessary. In this case, the opinions of several scientists on a specific topic are studied, and the student supports the idea he likes.

Online method of studying ecology and nature conservation. Times are developing so quickly that even when studying ecology and nature conservation, technical means help to conduct lessons. As in all areas, new technologies are happening in environmental pedagogy, as a result of which the level of assimilation of this knowledge by students increases, and the student has the opportunity to learn and feel natural phenomena that are very far from him. Video films, slide projectors, computer displays have already entered university classrooms, and today the methodology of conducting online classes is being formed. The advantage of this method is that students can listen to lectures by the most knowledgeable scientists of the country and answer questions online. Ponomareva O. N. (2008) writes that video films, video projectors and computer programs allow a student to quickly and easily perceive natural phenomena and environmental crises.

Summary. The university student receives the environmental education he needs, knowing and applying a number of methods. The student not only consolidates knowledge about nature, but also learns the laws that preserve biological diversity, natural communities, natural relationships that protect nature, as well as the role of a person who boldly protects nature. By studying these methods, each student chooses those methods that he considers convenient, and then uses them in studying natural sciences, the student's methodological curiosity increases, his social activity in nature conservation increases, and the opportunity arises to further improve his knowledge. The student will strengthen the unity of knowledge and education, while the professional training of the future teacher will improve. Regardless of the method used in environmental education, it is impossible to use real environmental technologies in nature and establish a real environmental order without continuity, diversity of the educational system, without the formation of environmental awareness in students. During classes, conducting pedagogical activities using the most modern methods will have a positive effect in combining the information received in the study of environmental relationships, environmental and educational significance.

REFERENCES

1. Kavtaradze D. N. // Towards Sustainable Development. - 1997. - No. 2 (6). - 38-45 p.
2. Kavtaradze, D. N. Why do we need environmental education? Instructions and reference materials for game teachers-managers. - 25 p.
3. Lerner, I. Da. Didactic foundations of teaching methods / I. Da. Lerner. - M.:, 1981 Pedagogy. - 186 p.

4. 184. Malozemova I. Ya. Development of environmental education in a modern university. International scientific and practical conference on the topic "Biological and environmental education in schools and universities: theory, methodology, practice 2017". 127-131 p.
5. 192. Makhmutov M.I. Problem-based education: main issues of theory. - Moscow: Pedagogy, 368 p.
6. Reutova E. A. Application of active and interactive teaching methods in the educational process of higher education (methodical recommendations for teachers of the Osibirsk State University). - Novosibirsk: Publishing House of the Novosibirsk State Agrarian University, 2012. - 58 p.
7. Surovegina I. T. The system of environmental education in school: concept and model / I. T. Surovegina // Ecology, culture, education: materials of the Kkonf. - M., 1989. Pp. 180-187.
8. Ponomareva O. N. Ecology in school: methodological approaches to education / Penza: 1999. 77 p.
9. Cheredov I. M. Forms of educational work in a comprehensive school: a book for teachers. Moscow: Education, 1988. 26 p.
10. M., Bakhadirov Z, Yakubzhanov Sh, Khaidarov. Methods of teaching ecology. Tashkent. Financial economy. 2009. 217 p.